

PREPARING FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TO ORGANIZE “4K” EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES AS AN URGENT PEDAGOGICAL ISSUE

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ABSTRACT

In this article discussed about preparing future primary school teachers to organize “4k” educational processes as an urgent pedagogical issue.

In recent years, significant attention has been paid to improving the legal foundations of organizing educational processes in the education system, including higher education institutions. In particular, the new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” defines the main principles of state policy in the field of education. These principles include the prohibition of discrimination in education, ensuring equal opportunities for obtaining education, the incorporation of national and universal human values into education and upbringing, and the humanistic and democratic nature of education and upbringing.

Educational problems based on the competency-based approach have been widely studied in pedagogy. Scholars such as U. Inoyatov, N. Muslimov, O. Musurmonova, B. Khodjaev, M. Vahobov, M. Mirsolieva, and M. Paradaeva have made significant contributions to the development of the theoretical foundations of implementing the competency-based approach.

Researchers working on this issue have clarified the concept of competence through the concept of competency. Therefore, it is necessary to first provide a definition of the term “competence.”

Competence (Latin *competencia*) represents the range of issues in which a person is well-informed and possesses knowledge and experience.

The term “competence” was first used in 1965 by N. Chomsky. In his work “Aspects of the Theory of Syntax,” he proposed using the concept of “competence” to describe certain idealized objects that manifest under ideal conditions of activity (according to Chomsky: in language learning, under ideal communicative conditions).

In the chapter titled “Transformational Grammar as a Theory of Linguistic Competence,” Chomsky does not refer to the notion of competence but distinguishes it from performance: competence refers to knowledge about something (Chomsky: the knowledge of the speaker-hearer in their language), while performance is the actual use of that knowledge in practice—they are fundamentally different concepts.

Competence (from the Latin word meaning “to achieve” or “to correspond”) is the readiness of a subject to effectively organize internal and external resources to achieve a goal; in other words, it is an individual’s personal ability to solve specific professional problems.

According to N. Muslimov, the English term “competence” literally means “ability,” but the term competence is used to express knowledge, skills, proficiency, and ability.

V. Zolotseva interprets competence as “a general ability based on knowledge, values, and skills that ensures the relationship between knowledge and situation, knowledge and action to solve a problem.” From this perspective, competence can be defined as a person’s ability to solve a particular problem based on existing knowledge and life experience.

B. Khodjaev notes that most definitions of competence are given in the context of vocational education and professional activity. However, in relation to general secondary education, this concept has an innovative character, making it necessary to clarify its essence. He concludes that competence is the ability of a student to exceed the social requirements (standards) set for educational preparation necessary for effective and productive activity in a certain field.

There are various approaches to classifying types of competence. For example, N.A. Muslimov and M.B. Urazova, from the perspective of vocational education, distinguish the following types of competence:

- **Special competence** – mastering one’s professional activity at a sufficient level and planning further professional development;

- **Social competence** – mastering collaborative professional activity, cooperation, and social responsibility for the results of one’s work;

- **Personal competence** – mastering independent reflection and personal development, resisting professional deformation;

- **Individual competence** – independently applying and developing individuality within the profession, readiness for personal and professional growth, self-organization, and rehabilitation;

- **Basic competencies** – intercultural and interdisciplinary knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for adaptation and productive activity.

O. Hayitov and N. Umarov propose a cluster approach to grouping competencies:

- **Competencies related to information processing:** collecting and analyzing information, decision-making, transforming information;

- **Competencies for achieving success:** planning, organizing activities, analyzing results;

- **Competencies for working with people:** managing relationships, working in a team, influencing others;

- **Competencies for self-improvement:** self-assessment, professional growth, innovative mobility.

Ye.S. Zair-Bek identifies the following types of methodological competencies:

- **Goal-oriented competence:** the ability to set and clarify goals, which is a fundamental component of pedagogical activity and affects its outcomes;

- **Content competence:** the content of technological education within the framework of general educational preparation, minimum requirements for students' readiness, and maximum workload per year;

- **Monitoring competence:** assessing the quality of education, which involves evaluating educational results as well as the content, conditions, and processes that ensure those results.

M.B. Urazova, from the perspective of project-based activity, proposes the following types of competencies:

- **Reflective competence:** self-evaluation, self-demanding attitude toward one's achievements and shortcomings, understanding the causes of successes and failures;

- **Cognitive competence:** independently acquiring new knowledge and skills, applying ideas for independent development;

- **Information competence:** mastering special abilities for obtaining, processing, and using necessary information;

- **Communicative competence:** methods facilitating high-level communication;

- **Social competence:** understanding the social significance of reality, taking responsibility, and linking personal interests with societal needs.

The research shows that there is no universally accepted definition of competence or a unified classification of competencies. However, analysis indicates common approaches in foreign and national pedagogy and highlights the acmeological orientation of personal competence.

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